

ANTONYMS AND THEIR ROLE IN THE UZBEK LANGUAGE

Shodmonov Muhammadsodiq Navruz og'li

Student of the Faculty of Philology, Alfraganus University

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Abstract. This article examines the concept of antonyms, their role in language, and the nature of semantic opposition between words. The importance of antonyms in enriching the language and strengthening its expressive power is analyzed through examples. The paper also explains the differences between root-based and derived antonyms, the formation of antonyms through derivational affixes, and their position within parts of speech. Moreover, the stylistic function of antonyms in proverbs and sayings is discussed, showing how they serve as a means to reflect people's thinking and spiritual values.

Аннотация.

В данной статье рассматривается понятие антонимов, их роль в языке и характер семантической противоположности между словами. На основе примеров анализируется значение антонимов в обогащении языка и усилении его выразительных возможностей. В работе также объясняются различия между корневыми и производными антонимами, образование антонимов с помощью словообразовательных аффиксов и их место в системе частей речи. Кроме того, обсуждается стилистическая функция антонимов в пословицах и поговорках, показывающая, как они служат средством отражения народного мышления и духовных ценностей.

Keywords: антоним, антонимия, лексика, части речи, противоположное значение, пословица, поговорка, богатство языка

Ключевые слова: антоним, антонимия, лексика, части речи, противоположное значение, пословица, поговорка, богатство языка

Introduction

Language is the main tool for expressing human thought. Each word has its own meaning and emotional connotation. The richness and expressive power of a language are largely determined by the interrelations among its words. One such relationship is antonymy — the semantic opposition between words. Words that express opposite or contrasting meanings in relation to each other are called antonyms.¹

Antonymy (from Greek *antonymo* — “opposite name”) is a semantic relationship of contrast between lexemes: big – small, young – old, tiny – huge, white – black, etc. An antonymic pair must share a general semantic component while simultaneously expressing opposing meanings. For example, the lexemes big and small share the general notion of “quality” or “scale,” yet differ semantically as “relatively large” (big) and “relatively small” (small).²

Since antonymy is based on semantic contrast, a polysemous word may have different antonyms for its different meanings. For instance, the Uzbek word *qattiq* (“hard”) may mean “firm” in one context and “stingy” in another, thus forming different antonymic pairs such as *qattiq – yumshoq* (“hard – soft”) and *qattiq – saxiy* (“stingy – generous”).³

¹ Sh.Rahmatullayev, N.Mamatov, R.Shukurov O'zbek tili antonimlarining izohli lug'ati "O'qituvchi" nashriyoti T – 1989 B – 7

² R. R. Sayfullayeva, B. R. Mengliyev, L. R. Raupova, M. M. Qurbonova, M. Q. Abuzalova, D. N. Yo'ldosheva Hozirgi o'zbek tili "Innovatsiya-Ziyo" T – 2020 B – 133

³ Sh.Shoabdurahmonov, M.Asqarova, A.Xojiyev, I.Rasulov, X.Doniyorov Hozirgi o'zbek adabiy tili 1-qism "O'qituvchi" nshriyoti T – 1980 B - 119

Antonyms most often occur among adjectives and adverbs that denote qualities or states: yaxshi – yomon (“good – bad”), baland – past (“high – low”), tor – keng (“narrow – wide”), tez – sekin (“fast – slow”).

A part of adjectival antonyms is derived using affixes that express affirmation (-li, bo-) or negation (-siz, be-, no-), for example: baxtli – baxtsiz (“happy – unhappy”), aqlli – beaql (“wise – foolish”), insofli – noinsof (“fair – unfair”). However, not all such affixed forms are true antonyms. If the derived word does not convey a completely new lexical meaning or lacks a corresponding root word in the language, it cannot be considered a true antonym. For example, kuchli – kuchsiz (“strong – weak”) are true antonyms because each has a synonymic equivalent (zo‘r – zaif), while daftarli – daftarsiz (“with notebook – without notebook”) do not function as antonyms since they lack independent lexical value.⁴

Structurally, antonyms are divided into two types:

1. Different-root antonyms: katta – kichik (“big – small”), kirmoq – chiqmoq (“enter – exit”), muhabbat – nafrat (“love – hate”).

2. Same-root antonyms: madaniyatli – madaniyatsiz (“cultured – uncultured”), aqlli – beaql (“wise – foolish”), ongli – ongsiz (“conscious – unconscious”).⁵

According to R. R. Sayfullayeva, B. R. Mengliyev, L. R. Raupova, M. M. Qurbonova, M. Q. Abuzalova, and D. N. Yuldosheva, antonyms are classified based on whether their roots are identical or different.

Antonyms also serve as an important stylistic device in proverbs and sayings, enhancing their expressiveness and allowing general life experiences to be conveyed in a concise, artistic form:

Summer labor – winter comfort.

Work brings friends, gossip brings enemies.

A friend speaks bitterly, an enemy makes you laugh.

Work brings glory to the wise, sorrow to the foolish.⁶

Various parts of speech — nouns, adjectives, pronouns, verbs, etc. — can form antonymic pairs. They reflect human emotions, states, and activities, as well as natural phenomena, spatial and temporal relations, color, size, and other characteristics.

Antonyms specific to adjectives:

Size: big–small, high–low;

Condition: hot–cold, young–old;

Quality: generous–stingy, intelligent–foolish;

Shape: straight–crooked;

Taste: bitter–sweet.

Antonyms specific to adverbs mostly express meanings related to place and distance: here–there, far–near;

Time: before–after;

⁴ Sh.Rahmatullayev, N.Mamatov, R.Shukurov O‘zbek tili antonimlarining izohli lug‘ati “O‘qituvchi” nashriyoti T – 1989 B – 7

⁵ R. R. Sayfullayeva, B. R. Mengliyev, L. R. Raupova, M. M. Qurbonova, M. Q. Abuzalova, D. N. Yo‘Ldosheva Hozirgi o‘zbek tili “Innovatsiya-Ziyo” T – 2020 B – 134

⁶ H.Jamolxonov Hozirgi o‘zbek adabiy tili Talqin nashriyoti T – 2005 B – 176

Manner: fast–slow;

Quantity: much–little;

Purpose: intentionally–accidentally.

Among nouns, there are also many antonyms. These include quality nouns such as wealth–poverty, bravery–cowardice; words denoting opposite directions like east–west, south–north; and those indicating opposite points of time and seasons such as spring–autumn, summer–winter, night–day, dawn–dusk.

In the verb category, antonyms are also common. They are mostly derived from adjective and adverb antonyms: to widen–to narrow, to increase–to decrease, to slow down–to speed up, etc. These verbs are formed from adjectives and adverbs that carry opposite meanings.⁷

Conclusion

Antonyms form an important layer of the linguistic system, expanding the semantic potential of words and enriching the expressiveness of language. They enable the clear and effective expression of opposing concepts, emotions, and states. The examples presented in the article demonstrate that antonyms function not only as lexical units but also as significant stylistic means. Therefore, the study of antonyms plays a vital role in understanding the semantic richness of a language and in improving practical usage in speech.

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⁷ Sh.Rahmatullayev, N.Mamatov, R.Shukurov O‘zbek tili antonimlarining izohli lug‘ati “O‘qituvchi” nashriyoti T – 1989 B – 8